

GEMINI PLENARY MEETING

3-4 JUNE 2024 – PORTO (PORTUGAL)

GEMINI partners held their annual general meeting in Porto, Portugal. The event featured **bilateral exchanges, workshops, and progress reports** on various workpackages, including **business models, impact assessment, and communication strategies**. Participants also visited the Estádio do Dragão to explore mobility management integration around the stadium. The meeting concluded with **strategic discussions and interactions** with other mobility projects, significantly advancing the GEMINI project's goals.

[READ MORE](#)

GEMINI'S MOBILITY LIVING LAB COPENHAGEN

Multimodal mobility hubs in greater Copenhagen peri-urban context

This Living Lab focuses on creating multimodal mobility hubs in Greater Copenhagen's peri-urban areas. These hubs aim to integrate public transport with shared mobility options, such as bikes and e-scooters, to reduce car dependency and improve accessibility.

[READ](#)

GEMINI'S MOBILITY LIVING LAB AMSTERDAM

Mobility as a Commons (MaaC)

This Living Lab introduces an alternative model for shared mobility governed by community cooperatives. This approach aims to address social mobility needs, making transport more inclusive and sustainable. The pilot project offers cooperative car-sharing permits at no cost, promoting zero-emission transport modes like electric cars and bikes.

[READ](#)

GEMINI SITE VISIT IN HELSINGBORG

The GEMINI project team visited Helsingborg, Sweden, to study shared mobility solutions, including the management of e-scooters and the development of shared mobility hubs. This visit provided valuable insights and ideas for enhancing micromobility in the regions of Rudersdal, Helsingborg, and Helsingør.

[READ](#)

GEMINI MLL3 MUNICH

Allianz arena Living Lab Workshop (March 5-6)

The GEMINI MLL3 Munich workshop at Allianz Arena on March 5-6 gathered partners to discuss mobility management during sports events. Key activities included traffic and parking modeling, a fan survey on transport preferences, and observing real-life stadium traffic conditions.

[READ](#)

CONTRIBUTE TO THE NEW PODCAST SERIES

The [Townmaking Institute](#) recently instituted a **Podcast series** to express the urgency for local-scale resilience through the growth of Commons. We would like to **invite other partners** who want to build local Commons to **start regional podcasts**, both in local languages and in English. The Townmaking Institute will provide the necessary **style guides and training**, following the NextCommons principles, to help you start your own podcasts to promote local Commons development.

To contribute contact the dissemination team

RELATED PROJECTS

Starting in January, GEMINI is pleased to announce its synergy with two projects: the SUM Project and the ReMuNet Project.

[More info on their websites.](#)

Next Events

GEMINI partners can register for events using the dissemination plan.

You're receiving this email because you're signed up to our mailing list. You can unsubscribe [here](#).

[JOIN THE NEWSLETTER](#)